

TYPES OF MEDIATION AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

This article is of scientific-pedagogical importance and shows the five stages of mediation, taking into account the international experience. In addition, it discusses different types of mediation and the specific characteristics of each type, and it offers suggestions and recommendations on the correct use of mediation types.

Keywords: alternative dispute resolution, dispute resolution system, mediation, mediation services, mediation methods, negotiation

Aims and objectives: To form the student's knowledge and skills on the stages of mediation by discussing each stage of mediation. Also, based on the international experience, analyze the types of mediation and study the practice of their application.

Introduction

Conflict is a natural part of life. When managed intentionally, conflict can positively change lives and relationships. Mediation has gained considerable popularity in recent years as a form of alternative dispute resolution. It offers a confidential and cooperative process in which a neutral third party, the mediator, facilitates communication between the disputing parties. Mediation allows

individuals to take control of their conflict, develop understanding, and promote mutually agreed-upon solutions. Mediators are trained to understand the source of conflict, to move away from adversarial positions, and to identify a path toward positive growth and change. Mediators create a safe space for difficult conversations. We can divide mediation into several types according to the form of implementation or depending on the dispute being resolved. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Mediation” a mediator can resolve disputes arising from civil legal relations, including disputes arising from the implementation of entrepreneurial activities, as well as individual labor disputes and disputes arising from family legal relations. But if we look at the international experience, mediation has now become a form of alternative resolution for almost all types of disputes.

When considering mediation, it is easy to assume that the primary purpose of mediation is to resolve a dispute. Although settlement is one of the goals of mediation, the main goal of mediation is to enable the parties to fully understand their case and to know the best option or course of action for their case. A good mediator can listen to the parties, see the main interest of the party beyond just the financial one, and help each party understand that interest as a way to resolve the case in a positive way.

Main body

Understanding the types of mediation is an important skill in preparing for and participating in mediation. Knowing how a mediator works and what skills they use is important for the parties and their counsel to work best with the mediator and determine what is important to them. This is an important skill for mediators as well, because although each mediator has a unique style, they are bound to come across a conflict where a different type of mediation would be useful. The types or methods of mediation are evident in the control that the mediator exercises during the

mediation process. Some types of mediation exercise more control and have more of a say in the mediation, while other mediators allow the parties to set up the conversation.

Mediation usually takes place in five stages. These stages differ depending on the role of the participants. It may seem strange, but since the goals and roles of the mediator and the party or disputant are different, they tend to go through different stages. Below, we can see the five main stages of mediation:

1. Summons: Summons is the initial conversation between the mediator and the parties agreeing to mediate. The parties can decide whether they want to mediate or whether the dispute is ready for mediation. The parties also begin to prepare for mediation.

2. Opening Statement: The opening statement is the mediator's description of the process, including how to describe the legal rights and assessments.

3. Communication: Communication is the stage where the parties share their needs and desires for the mediation process. This is usually done in a large group setting, and all parties listen and evaluate the issues.

4. Negotiations: Negotiations are the stage where the parties work with a mediator to present offers and counter-offers to each other. Depending on the mediator's style, they may play a role here in evaluating and suggesting options, or they may allow the parties to negotiate and find common ground.

5. Conclusion: After the parties negotiate, they either settle or decide they are too far apart to settle and walk away without an agreement. This assessment may be made by the parties, or the mediator may feel that the parties are unable to reach an agreement and suggest that the mediation end.

Finding, understanding, and improving mediation techniques can help everyone involved in mediation fully participate and resolve the issue. Although all

mediators work to help parties resolve disputes, they use different techniques and approaches to do so. Just as doctors and counselors use different strategies to achieve desired outcomes, mediators use different techniques. Now let's talk about each type of mediation separately.

The first is evaluative mediation. Evaluative mediation is a mediation style in which the mediator exercises the most control during the mediation and has the most voice about the parties' positions and their proposals. The evaluative mediator provides feedback on the parties' strengths and weaknesses and monitors how and when the parties interact. This mediation process works best when there is an uneven power dynamic in the mediation, such as in a typical divorce mediation or consumer v. company case, and allows the mediator to focus the conversation on the important issues and what the parties need. An evaluative mediator is likely to be appreciated for his no-nonsense style. Evaluative mediators work quickly and efficiently to reach an issue and find a solution. They consider more options and make recommendations based on their experience. Evaluative mediators are especially useful when time is short and the issue is relatively clear, the case may end up in court, or the parties want recommendations from a neutral party. In direct contrast to facilitative mediation, it is a type of mediation in which mediators are more likely to make recommendations and provide feedback. Instead of focusing primarily on the primary interests of the parties involved, evaluative mediators can help the parties evaluate the legal merits of their arguments and determine fairness. Evaluative mediation is often used in court-ordered mediation, and evaluative mediators are often attorneys with legal expertise in the area of dispute.

Evaluative mediation is a specific style of mediation that can be very helpful for parties who are unsure of their positions and need someone to evaluate their case and make suggestions. It can also be useful for parties who are not good at expressing

their needs and interests directly to the other party. Evaluative mediation allows the parties to consider their strengths and weaknesses and has a neutral assessment of the strength of the case.

The second is transformative mediation. A mediator with a transformative approach can be valued for the time and space he creates for all parties to truly hear and understand each other. Transformative mediators can create more space for emotional expression through the process and support emotional healing along with resolution. Transformative mediators are particularly useful when disputes involve deeper personal issues, including identity and relationships, and when the parties seek empowerment and recognition. In transformative mediation, mediators focus on enhancing conflict resolution and encouraging them to recognize each other's needs and interests. This process focuses on changing the parties and their relationships by acquiring the skills necessary to effect constructive change for the greater good.

The third is facilitative mediation. This is the type of mediation most people are familiar with. Facilitative mediators are used for adaptation methods based on the dynamic needs of the parties. They can use evaluation and modification methods. Using a facilitative style, the mediator asks questions, normalizes perspectives, and validates the viewpoints of both parties. In facilitative mediation, or traditional mediation, a professional mediator tries to facilitate negotiations between disputing parties. Instead of making recommendations or making decisions, the mediator encourages the parties to reach their own voluntary resolution by exploring each other's interests in depth. In facilitative mediation, mediators tend to hide their views on the dispute.

The fourth is court-mandated mediation. Although mediation is generally described as an entirely voluntary process, it may be conducted by a court interested

in reaching a speedy and cost-effective settlement. If the parties and their attorneys do not wish to engage in mediation, they have the option of resolving through court-ordered mediation. But when parties on both sides see the benefits of participating in the process, settlement rates are much higher.

The fifth is Med-Arb, or Arb-Med. In Med-Arb, a mediation-arbitration hybrid, the parties first agree on the terms of the process itself. Unlike most mediations, they usually agree in writing that the outcome of the process will be binding. Later, they try to negotiate a settlement of their dispute with the help of a mediator. If the mediation reaches an impasse or the issues are not resolved, the process is not over. At this point, the parties may proceed to arbitration. The mediator may assume the role of an arbitrator (if he is qualified to do so) and may quickly make a binding decision based on his judgment on the case as a whole or on outstanding issues. Alternatively, the arbitrator may take over the case after consulting with the mediator. Another type of mediation in arb-med, a trained, neutral third party hears the arguments and testimony of the disputants in the arbitration court, prepares a judgment or decision based on the results, but keeps it from the parties; if the parties attempt to mediate the dispute, and if the parties cannot reach an agreement, they will be forced to follow its previously determined mandatory judgment.

The sixth is electronic (online) mediation. In electronic mediation, the mediator provides mediation services to parties who are located far from each other or whose conflict is intense. Electronic mediation can be a fully automated online dispute resolution system with no third-party interaction at all. But e-mediation is similar to traditional facilitated mediation conducted remotely. Thanks to video conferencing services such as Zoom, Skype, and Google Hangouts, parties can now easily and inexpensively communicate with each other in real time while also using

visual and audio cues. Early research findings suggest that technology-enhanced mediation can be as effective as traditional meditation techniques. In addition, parties often find it a low-stress process that instills trust and positive feelings.

Conclusion. By studying different types of mediation, we have not only expanded our understanding of this powerful tool for conflict resolution but also seen how mediation can be adapted in different contexts. Each type offers unique characteristics, advantages, and limitations, catering to the different needs and preferences of parties involved in disputes. Whether it is a facilitative approach that promotes dialogue and self-determination, an evaluative approach that focuses on legal standards, or a transformative approach that emphasizes empowerment and personal growth, mediation is a range of conflict resolution approaches. provides options. As we continue to live in an ever-changing world, we must seek to understand and embrace these different types of mediation to pave the way for more effective, collaborative, and sustainable decisions. Mediation seeks to help the parties understand their situations and find an agreement that emphasizes their strengths and needs. A professional mediator has discretion in conducting mediation and can select a style based on the needs of the parties. It's common for mediators to even try more than one of these styles. Knowing how a mediator works and uses a style can be the best preparation a party can bring to the mediation table, as it allows a party to articulate their position within the style and helps the mediator and the parties involved understand the position. Understanding the types of mediation and finding an appropriate style for the dispute can help participants feel confident in their decisions and gain a deeper understanding of the case.

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